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Title: Supramolecular solvent-based microextraction of Ochratoxin A in raw wheat prior to liquid chromatography/fluorescence determination

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36 **Abstract**

37

38 A supramolecular solvent made up of reverse micelles of decanoic acid, dispersed in a continuous
39 phase of THF:water, was proposed for the simple, fast and efficient microextraction of OTA in wheat prior
40 to liquid chromatography/fluorescence determination. The method involved the stirring of 300 mg-wheat
41 subsamples (particle size 50 μm) and 350 μL of supramolecular solvent for 15 min, subsequent
42 centrifugation for 15 min and the direct quantitation of OTA in the extract, previous 5.7-fold dilution with
43 ethanol/water/acetic acid (49.5/49.5/1), against solvent-based calibration curves. No clean-up of the
44 extracts or solvent evaporation was needed. Interactions between the supramolecular solvent and major
45 matrix components in the wheat (i.e. carbohydrates, lipids and proteins) were investigated. The reverse
46 micelles in the extractant induced gluten flocculation but only in the coacervation region of lower analytical
47 interest (i.e. at percentages of THF above 11%). The quantitation of OTA was interference-free.
48 Representativity of the 300 mg-wheat subsamples was proved by analysing a reference material. OTA
49 recoveries in wheat ranged between 84 and 95% and the precision of the method, expressed as relative
50 standard deviation, was 2%. The quantitation limit of the method was 1.5 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$ and was below the
51 threshold limit established for OTA in raw cereals by EU directives (5.0 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$). The method developed
52 was validated by using a certified reference material and it was successfully applied to the determination
53 of OTA in different wheat varieties from crops harvested in the South of Spain. OTA was not detected in
54 any of the analysed samples. This method allows quick and simple microextraction of OTA with minimal
55 solvent consumption, while delivering accurate and precise data.

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58 **Keywords:** Wheat; Supramolecular solvent; Ochratoxin A; Liquid chromatography; Fluorescence
59 detection

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73 1. Introduction

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75 Ochratoxin A (OTA) is one of the most widespread and hazardous mycotoxins contaminating
76 foodstuffs [1]. It is produced by several fungi (*Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* species) in a variety of plant
77 products, such as cereals, pulses, coffee, wine, grape juice, dried fruits and spices [2]. OTA is considered
78 a potent nephrotoxic and genotoxic agent [3] and has been classified as a possible human carcinogen
79 (group 2B) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer [4]. Monitoring OTA in cereals has
80 become an important issue worldwide due to both the impact on human health and the high economic
81 losses associated to crop production. In fact, among the most frequently contaminated food commodities,
82 cereals are the main European dietary source of OTA (44%), increasing this value in the case of Spain
83 (60%) [5]. The European Union has established maximum residue levels (MRLs) of OTA in raw cereals
84 and derived products of 5 and 3 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, respectively [6].

85 Several official methods are available for surveillance of OTA residues in cereals and cereal
86 products (e.g., barley [7-10], wheat flour [11], barley, wheat bran and corn [12] and wheat, rye and corn
87 [9]). Liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection (LC-FL), which provides quantitation limits
88 between 0.1 and 10 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, is by far the most used technique for OTA determination. Recoveries and
89 relative standard deviations for these methods range in the intervals 65-100% and 10-20%, respectively.
90 On the other hand, several non-official LC-FL methods, affording recoveries above 75%, have been
91 reported [13-15]; many of them constituting a good alternative to official methods in terms of sensitivity,
92 reproducibility and/or simplicity. Immunochemical methods, highlighting immunosensors based on enzyme
93 linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) [16], have been proposed as simple on-site screening methods
94 (detection limits in the $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$ range).

95 Due to the complexity of food matrices, sample preparation (extraction, concentration and clean-
96 up) is essential in OTA analysis. Solvent extraction is by far the most used strategy for isolation of OTA
97 from cereals and derived products. A variety of solvents and solvent mixtures, including acidified
98 chloroform [9,10,12,17], methanol-aqueous bicarbonate [15], methanol-phosphate buffer [18,19], acidified
99 toluene-magnesium chloride [11] and acetonitrile-water [7,8,20], have been proposed. The volume of
100 organic solvent consumed per sample is relatively high (50-250 mL) and after extraction, further clean-up
101 is usually needed. Immunoaffinity chromatography (IAC) is widely used for sample clean-up (8,15,17-21),
102 although other approaches, including purification through a silica gel column [11], defatting with n-hexane
103 [17] or filtration through diatomaceous earth followed by back-extraction with aqueous bicarbonate and
104 purification through C_{18} cartridges [9,10,12], are being also used. Recently, new strategies including matrix
105 solid phase dispersion (MSDP), which combines extraction and clean-up in one step and considerably
106 reduces solvent consumption [22], and molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP), which provide selectivity
107 comparable to IAC without the cost of producing antibodies [23], have been reported. So far, IAC
108 surpasses other reported clean-up methods in versatility (e.g. it is applicable to a wider range of matrices),
109 selectivity (e.g., it provides cleaner extracts and consequently lower quantification limits) and

110 reproducibility (e.g., usually, relative standard deviations are below 5%) [15,17]. However, IAC presents
111 important disadvantages for routine analysis; immunoaffinity columns are expensive, not recyclable, have
112 a limited storage time and, in some cases, show cross-reactivity with Ochratoxin C [24].

113 According to the state of the art in this field, new methods intended to improve OTA determination
114 in cereals should focus on simplifying sample preparation making it faster, cheaper and environmentally
115 friendly (i.e., by reducing considerably solvent consumption) while keeping method sensitivity below the
116 legislative limits and enough selectivity. In this context, this paper explores the suitability of
117 supramolecular solvents to simplify sample treatment in the determination of OTA in wheat.
118 Supramolecular solvents are water-immiscible liquids made up of supramolecular assemblies dispersed in
119 a continuous phase. They are produced from amphiphile solutions by a sequential self assembly process
120 occurring on two scales, molecular and nano, and constitute a valuable strategy to replace organic solvents
121 in analytical extraction processes. First, amphiphilic molecules spontaneously form three-dimensional
122 aggregates above a critical aggregation concentration, mainly aqueous (size 3-6 nm) or reversed (size 4-8
123 nm) micelles and vesicles (size 30–500 nm), depending on the structure of amphiphiles and solvent
124 properties. Then, the generated nanostructures self-assemble in larger aggregates, with a wide size
125 distribution in the nano and micro scale regimes, by the action of an external stimulus (e.g. temperature,
126 electrolyte, pH, solvent) and separate from the bulk solution as an immiscible liquid by a phenomenon
127 named coacervation. To date, supramolecular solvents from a variety of surfactant aggregates, i.e. non-
128 ionic [25], zwitterionic [26], cationic [27] and anionic [28] aqueous micelles, reversed micelles [29] and
129 vesicles [30] have been successfully used for the extraction of pollutants from the environment [31-34] and,
130 more recently, from foodstuffs [35,36].

131 In this paper, a supramolecular made up of decanoic acid reverse micelles, previously described
132 by our research group [29] was selected for the microextraction of OTA in raw wheat prior to LC/FL
133 determination. Selection was based on the different types of interactions (i.e., hydrogen bonding and
134 dispersion forces) it provides for OTA solubilisation and the high amphiphile concentration in the solvent
135 (around 0.75 mg μL^{-1}), all of which should give high extraction efficiencies. The aim was to develop a
136 simple, low-cost and rapid method for the routine control of this contaminant in wheat matrices.
137 Parameters affecting sample representativity, extraction efficiency and detection and quantification limits
138 were optimised and the method was successfully applied to the determination of OTA in different varieties
139 of wheat including bread and durum wheat and two synthetic wheat hybrids.

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141 **2. Experimental**

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143 *2.1. Chemicals*

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145 All chemicals were of analytical reagent-grade and were used as supplied. Tetrahydrofuran (THF),
146 HPLC-grade acetonitrile, methanol, ethanol and glacial acetic acid were supplied by Panreac (Sevilla,

147 Spain). Ultra-high-quality water was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system (Millipore, Madrid,
148 Spain). Decanoic acid was purchased from Fluka (Madrid, Spain), while starch, gluten from wheat and
149 ochratoxin A (OTA) were obtained from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). The certified reference material
150 BCR471 (an OTA free wheat) was obtained from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA) and the reference material
151 OW815 batch (OTA content in wheat: 4.9 ± 1.0 ppb) was supplied by R-Biopharm (Glasgow, Scotland). A
152 stock standard solution of 10 mg L^{-1} of OTA was prepared in methanol and stored under dark conditions at
153 -20°C . Working solutions were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with methanol and calibration
154 solutions were made with a mixture of water/ethanol/acetic acid (49.5/49.5/1).

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156 2.2. Apparatus

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158 The liquid chromatographic system used (Spectra System SCM1000, ThermoQuest, San Jose, CA, USA)
159 consisted of a P2000 binary pump and a FL3000 fluorescence detector. In all experiments a PEEK
160 Rheodyne 7125NS injection valve with a $100 \mu\text{L}$ sample loop was used (ThermoQuest, San Jose, CA,
161 USA). The stationary-phase column was a Kromasil C_8 (25 cm x 4.6 mm i.d., $5 \mu\text{m}$) from Análisis Vínicos
162 (Tomelloso, Spain). A Retsch MM301 mixer mill and a Mixtasel Selecta centrifuge were employed for
163 sample preparation. Centrifuge tubes with narrow necks (Figure 1) were designed by authors in order to
164 make easier the measurement and collection of the supramolecular solvent after microextraction. Pobel
165 S.A. (Madrid, Spain, web page: www.pobel.com) constructed them from commercial heavy-duty glass
166 cylindrical centrifuge tubes with round-bottom (ref. 159050) by keeping their basic structure at the bottom
167 (34 mm of outside diameter) but reducing the diameter from a specified height, which depended on the
168 required tube capacity.

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170 2.3. Determination of OTA in wheat

171

172 2.3.1. Sample preparation and preservation

173 The cereal samples analyzed ($n=6$) were kindly supplied by the Department of Agronomy and
174 Genetic Improvement of the Spanish National Research Council (SNRC) of Córdoba (Spain) and
175 consisted of two durum wheat (*Triticum durum Desf*), two bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum L.*) and two
176 synthetic wheat hybrids, namely Triticale (*X Triticosecale spp.*, which is an hybrid from bread wheat and
177 rye) and Tritordeum (*Hordeum-Triticum*, which is an hybrid from a South American wild barley and durum
178 wheat [37]). Samples were supplied as 100 g-single bags. Aliquots of 25 g were ground and blended in a
179 Retsch MM301 mixer mill, in two steps (2 min each), at a vibrational frequency of 28 s^{-1} . This procedure
180 gave particle sizes below $50 \mu\text{m}$. Aliquots of 300 mg were subsequently subjected to microextraction with
181 the supramolecular solvent. Otherwise, the samples were vacuum-packaged in foil-laminate pouches,
182 heat-sealed and stored at -4°C until their analysis. Figure 1 outlines the sequential steps followed for the
183 determination of OTA in wheat including subsampling, microextraction and quantitation.

184

185 2.3.2. *Supramolecular solvent-based microextraction*

186 A wheat subsample (300 mg) was introduced in a specially designed 10 mL-glass centrifuge
187 tube (Fig. 1) and then, decanoic acid (300 mg) dissolved in THF (0.8 mL) and 9.2 mL of water (pH 2.7
188 adjusted with hydrochloric acid) were added in sequence. Immediately, a volume of around 350 μ L of
189 supramolecular solvent, immiscible with the THF:water mixture, separated from the bulk solution. The
190 mixture was stirred at 1500 rpm for 15 minutes to favour analyte partition and then centrifuged at 2400 g
191 for 15 min to accelerate the complete separation of the two immiscible liquids. The supramolecular
192 solvent, which was standing at the top of the solution into the narrow neck of the tube, was withdrawn with
193 a microsyringe and transferred to a 2-mL calibrated flask. Then, it was diluted to the mark with a mixture of
194 ethanol/water/glacial acetic acid (54/45/1), filtered (0.45 μ m filters) and 100 μ L-aliquots were injected in
195 the LC/FL system.

196

197 2.3.3. *Liquid chromatography-fluorescence detection*

198 Quantification of OTA was carried out by LC-FL. The mobile phase consisted of water (solvent A)
199 and acetonitrile (solvent B), both containing 1% acetic acid. The elution program was: isocratic conditions
200 (55% of A and 45% of B) for 5 min, linear gradient from 55% to 50% in A for 10 min, then linear gradient
201 from 50% to 0% in A for 5 min and , finally, 5 min more from 0 to 55% in A to recover initial conditions. The
202 flow-rate was 1 mL min⁻¹. OTA was monitored at λ_{ex} 334 nm and λ_{em} 460 nm. Quantification was
203 performed by measuring peak areas. Calibration curves for OTA in ethanol/water/glacial acetic acid
204 (54/45/1) were constructed in the range 0.2-10 μ g L⁻¹.

205

206 **3. Results and discussion**

207

208 3.1. *Supramolecular solvent-wheat interactions: analytical consequences*

209

210 A good knowledge of the interactions between extractant and matrix is essential to prevent
211 interferences and set up efficient extraction schemes, so before optimization of the extraction procedure
212 we investigated the major interactions occurring between the supramolecular solvent and wheat.
213 Considering that most of raw and processed foods contain similar constituents (e.g. carbohydrates, lipids,
214 proteins, etc), the conclusions derived of this study can be probably extended to other applications
215 involving supramolecular solvent microextractions of contaminants in food.

216

217 The supramolecular solvent selected for OTA microextraction consists of decanoic acid reverse
218 micelles, with a wide size distribution in the nano and micro-scale regimes, dispersed in a THF:water
219 continuous phase [29]. It spontaneously forms in a ternary system made up of decanoic acid, THF and
water at the proportions shown in Figure 2A. Solvent production occurs in two well-defined steps; first,

220 decanoic acid dissolves in THF forming typical reverse micelles according to a sequential type self-
221 association, and second, decanoic acid reassembles in larger micellar aggregates under water addition
222 and separate from the bulk solution as an immiscible liquid. This liquid-liquid phase separation
223 phenomenon, named coacervation [38], is mainly caused by the water-induced partial desolvation of
224 reverse micelles (water is a non-solvent for decanoic acid) which makes their interaction easier and
225 favours their rearrangement in larger aggregates. Major components of the supramolecular solvent are
226 decanoic acid and THF; water is a minor constituent.

227 The volume of solvent produced depends on the amount of decanoic acid ($y = a + bx$) and the
228 percentage of THF ($y = b_0 e^{b_1 z}$) [34]. In these equations, y is given in μL , x is the amount of decanoic acid
229 in mg, and z the THF percentage (v/v). The linear relationship between y and x indicates that the
230 composition of the supramolecular solvent keeps constant as the percentage of THF in the bulk solution
231 remains unchanged. On the other hand, the exponential relationship between y and z reveals that the
232 volume of THF incorporated into the supramolecular solvent increases as the percentage of THF used to
233 produce it does, which results in decreased surfactant concentration in the supramolecular solvent.

234 Concerning wheat, carbohydrates (mainly as starch), proteins (mainly as gluten), lipids and water
235 are the main constituents of this cereal, the relative percentages depending on wheat variety. These
236 percentages range between around 71-75, 10-14, 2-2.5 and 10.5-11 %, respectively, for the wheat
237 varieties analysed [39-41].

238 The influence of wheat matrix components on supramolecular solvent formation and volume was
239 investigated. Figure 2B shows the phase diagram obtained in the presence of 300 mg of wheat,
240 independently of the variety tested. By comparison with Figure 2A, it is clearly observed that the upper
241 boundary moved toward lower THF percentages (around 11%), owing to the apparition of a dense whitish
242 precipitate that was standing at the interface between the supramolecular solvent and the bulk solution, as
243 a very thin layer, after centrifugation. This layer became wider as the percentage of THF in the bulk
244 solution increased, until the entire clear upper liquid phase corresponding to the supramolecular solvent
245 was completely adsorbed by the precipitate at around 25% THF. This behaviour was pH-dependent;
246 precipitation being favoured at the lowest pHs (e.g. the upper boundary in the phase diagram moved
247 around 8% of THF at pH 2).

248 In order to explain the observed phenomenon, phase diagrams were constructed in the presence
249 of starch and gluten, as representative of carbohydrates and proteins, respectively, at the maximal
250 concentrations these constituents are usually found in wheat (i.e. 225 mg of starch and 42 mg of gluten
251 per 300 mg of sample). The pH in these experiments ranged between 1.5 and 4. Starch did not influence
252 phase diagrams but gluten flocculated in the presence of decanoic acid reverse micelles and phase
253 diagrams were identical to those obtained in the presence of wheat (Figure 2B). Extraction of proteins by
254 reverse micelles has been previously reported in the literature [42] and their influence (e.g. albumin and
255 lysozyme) on the phase diagram of this supramolecular solvent has been described [43]. Flocculation of
256 gluten in the presence of the supramolecular solvent was favoured with increased percentages of THF

257 (above 11%) and low pHs (i.e. < 2), probably due to the higher global charge of the ionized protein (e.g.
258 increases of 50% in gluten solubility have been reported going from pH 6 to pH 2 [44]). From an analytical
259 point of view, it is worth noting that the effect of wheat proteins on the supramolecular solvent phase
260 diagram is not significant for extraction purposes, since analytical applications are usually carried out near
261 the lower phase boundary in order to use the minimal amount of THF for solvent production [29,34]. With
262 the aim of avoiding gluten flocculation, and having into account that the supramolecular solvent forms at
263 pH below 4, extraction of OTA in wheat should be carried out at pHs between about 2.5 and 4.

264 To study the influence of wheat constituents on the volume of solvent produced, a set of solutions
265 containing 300 mg of bread wheat, amounts of decanoic acid between 125 and 350 mg, THF percentages
266 between 4 and 11% and water (96-89%) were prepared. The volumes of supramolecular solvent obtained
267 were measure with a digital calliper and the relationships between these volumes and the amount of
268 decanoic acid and THF were investigated. Table 1 and 2 show the results obtained.

269 As expected, the volume of supramolecular solvent produced was linearly dependent on the
270 amount of surfactant used (Table 1), but the slopes of these linear relationships were around 10% below
271 those obtained in the absence of wheat [34], probably due to the adsorption of some decanoic acid on
272 matrix components. Accordingly, the volume of solvent produced decreased in around 20-40 μL in the
273 interval of decanoic acid tested. The y-intercepts were negative and different from zero, thus indicating
274 that more initial amount of surfactant was needed in bulk solutions containing wheat to start producing
275 supramolecular solvent.

276 The relationship between the volume of supramolecular solvent and the THF percentage was
277 exponential (Table 2). Similar to water, the parameter b_0 was linearly related to the amount of decanoic
278 acid. However, the parameter b_1 , which describes how rapidly the volume of coacervate increases as the
279 THF (%) does, did not keep constant (mean value for b_1 in water 0.046 ± 0.001 [34]) and it was
280 exponentially related to the decanoic acid amount, thus corroborating the interaction of the surfactant with
281 matrix components.

282 Because of supramolecular solvent volumes in the presence wheat were reproducible and related
283 to decanoic acid and THF through clear relationships, the reduction in around 10% compared to the
284 volumes obtained in the absence of wheat is irrelevant for analytical extraction processes. So, although
285 the reverse micelles in the supramolecular solvent are expected to flocculate proteins in food, the effects
286 produced (i.e. reduction of the proportions THF:water at which the supramolecular solvent forms and
287 decrease in solvent volume) should have not effect in extraction processes.

288

289 *3.2. Sample representativity study*

290

291 OTA is distributed irregularly in raw cereals due to the random nature of fungal contamination [2]
292 and this makes sampling and subsampling a major issue. Because of subsamples of at least 25 g are

293 recommended for analysis of cereals, reliable microextraction methods, based on the analysis of minute
294 amounts of sample, require a thorough sample homogenization prior to subsampling in order to achieve
295 representativity.

296 With the aim of obtaining homogeneous 25 g-samples and thus representative 300 mg-
297 subsamples, the influence of reducing the particle size on the accuracy of OTA microextraction was
298 investigated. For this purpose, the reference material CRM OW 815 (OTA concentration: $4.9 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$,
299 particle size $< 1 \text{ mm}$) was used as raw material. Experiments were carried out by extracting 300 mg-
300 subsamples ($n=11$) at three ranges of particle size (x), namely: a) $x < 1 \text{ mm}$, as supplied by the distributor;
301 b) $50 < x < 250 \mu\text{m}$, obtained after grounding 25 of the reference material with a ball crusher (Retsch
302 MM301 mixer mill; vibrational frequency 21.6 s^{-1} for 1 min, twice), and c) $x < 50 \mu\text{m}$, obtained by increasing
303 the vibrational frequency to 28 s^{-1} for 2 min, twice. Relative standard deviations (RSD) were calculated as
304 a measurement of homogeneity.

305 The results obtained for the analysis of $<1\text{mm}$ -material (RSD=96%) stood out the irregular
306 distribution of the mycotoxin, most of the amount of OTA determined being concentrated in just two of the
307 eleven aliquots analysed. The aspect of this material was heterogeneous in colour and texture and
308 included clearly visible dark particles corresponding to the wheat bran. The homogeneity moderately
309 increased for particle sizes in the interval $50 < x < 250 \mu\text{m}$ although the presence of outliers was still
310 observed (RSD=34%). A sharp decrease of the RSD value (3%) was found for the material with particle
311 size $<50 \mu\text{m}$, which also became uniform in colour. So, the later conditions were selected for OTA
312 microextraction with the supramolecular solvent.

313

314 3.3. *Optimisation of the supramolecular solvent-based microextraction of OTA*

315

316 OTA is a hydrophobic compound (its octanol-water partition coefficient; $\log K_{ow}$, is 4.74) and,
317 because of its pK_a values (4.4 for the acid group and 7.1 for the alcohol one), it is neutral at pH values
318 below 4, at which the solvent is produced. The sum of hydrogen donors and acceptors in OTA is 10. So,
319 the expected driving forces for OTA microextraction in the supramolecular solvent are Van der Waals
320 interactions between the hydrocarbon chains of the decanoic acid and the OTA aromatic framework, and
321 hydrogen bonds between the acceptor and donor groups of the analyte and the polar head-groups of the
322 surfactant.

323 Optimisation was carried out by extracting 300 mg of a blank certified reference material
324 (BCR471 wheat) fortified with $10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of OTA under a variety of experimental conditions (125-350 mg
325 decanoic acid; 4-11% THF; stirring time 0-60 min; pH between 2 and 4). Experiments were made in
326 triplicate. Selection of the optimal conditions was based on recoveries (R) in order to obtain the lower
327 quantification limits for the method, since concentration factors were maintained constant by diluting the
328 supramolecular solvent to 2 mL with a solvent mixture composition similar to that of the mobile phase;

329 ethanol/water/acetic acid (54/45/1). Spiking of samples was made by adding 150 μL of OTA ($20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in
330 methanol and left to stand for 1.5 hours to allow solvent evaporation at room temperature and favour
331 analyte-matrix interactions.

332 Table 3 shows the recoveries obtained along with their respective standard deviations as a
333 function of the main constituents of the supramolecular solvent (i.e. decanoic acid and THF). Maximal
334 recoveries were always obtained for THF percentages around 8%. The amount of OTA extracted
335 increased as the decanoic acid did and was maximal for 300 mg (i.e. at sample/decanoic acid ratios of 1).
336 Further studies were carried out with the aim of determining the interval of sample/decanoic acid ratios at
337 which recoveries were above 90%. For this purpose, amounts between 100 and 2000 mg of BCR471
338 wheat and between 150 and 300 mg of decanoic acid were combined to give wheat/decanoic acid ratios
339 from 0.33 to 13. Figure 3 shows the results obtained. Recoveries around 94% were obtained for
340 wheat/decanoic acid ratios below 1.2. From this value, recoveries progressively decreased until they kept
341 constant at around 25% for ratios above 2.5. Gluten precipitated from ratios around 13. According to these
342 results, the procedure can be resized at will provided that the amount of decanoic acid is similar to that of
343 wheat, although the representativity of wheat aliquots lower than 300 mg should thoroughly investigated
344 before their use for OTA determination. We selected 300 mg of both sample and decanoic for further
345 studies.

346 The pH did not influence recoveries in the range 2.5-4, which is logical considering the neutral
347 character of OTA in this interval and the type of interactions governing its solubilisation in the extractant.
348 The extraction time (stirring rate 1500 rpm) to reach equilibrium conditions was around 15 min and this
349 time was selected as optimal.

350 The high capability of the supramolecular solvent for the microextraction of OTA in wheat was
351 consequence of both the types of analyte-extractant interactions established and the special structure of
352 the aggregates making it up. Thus, recoveries for the extraction of OTA ($10 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) from wheat (BCR471
353 blank sample) with reverse micelles of decanoic acid in THF, at a decanoic acid concentration similar to
354 that found in the supramolecular solvent (e.g. 1400 mM), was only around 40%. THF and water were also
355 bad extractants for OTA with recoveries around 26 and 50% respectively.

356

357 *3.4. Analytical performance*

358

359 Calibration curves for OTA were run using standard solutions prepared in ethanol/water/acetic
360 acid (49.5/49.5/1). Because of the similar polarity of the injection solvent and the mobile phase, injection of
361 100 μL of sample extract did not cause broadening of the chromatographic peak for OTA. No differences
362 in peak areas or retention times were observed for the analytes injected in the standard solutions and the
363 supramolecular solvent ($\sim 350 \mu\text{L}$) diluted to 2 mL with a mixture of ethanol/water/acetic acid (54/45/1).
364 Correlation between peak areas and OTA concentration ($0.2\text{-}10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was determined by linear
365 regression and was 0.9991, indicating good fit. The slope of the calibration curve was $500 \pm 14 \text{ L } \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ ($n = 8$).

366 The instrumental quantitation (LOQ) and detection (LOD) limits were calculated from blank determinations
367 by using a signal-to-noise ratio of 10 and 3, respectively, and were 20 pg and 6.5 pg.

368 The method LOD and LOQ were estimated from the respective instrumental LOD and LOQ and
369 considering the amount of wheat (300 mg), the recoveries under optimum conditions (~94%) and the final
370 extract volume (2mL), and were 0.5 and 1.5 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, respectively. Since detection and quantitation limits
371 calculated in this way are often optimistic, the practical LOD and LOQ were calculated from six
372 independent complete determinations of blank wheat samples fortified with OTA in the range 0.5-3 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$
373 [45]. The practical LOQ and LOD were equal to those previously estimated, thus indicating the low matrix
374 influence in the method proposed

375 The possible interference of matrix components that could elute with OTA was assessed by the
376 comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves (n=8) obtained from standards in distilled water with
377 those obtained from wheat (BCR471) fortified with known amounts of OTA (1.5-40 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$) and run using
378 the whole procedure. The difference between both slopes ($519 \pm 12 \text{ L } \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ for water and $491 \pm 12 \text{ L } \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ for
379 wheat) was found to be not statistically significant by applying an appropriate Student's t test [45]. The
380 calculated t-value (1.74) was below the critical t-value (2.21), being significance established at 0.05 levels.
381 Therefore, matrix components were not expected to interfere in the determination of the target
382 compounds.

383 The precision of the method was evaluated by extracting seven independent samples (BCR471)
384 fortified with 8.0 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$ of OTA. The value, expressed as relative standard deviation (RSD), was about
385 2%.

386

387 *3.5. Method validation*

388

389 The method proposed was validated by analysing 300 mg-aliquots (n=11) of a reference material
390 (RM OW 815, R-Biopharm) consisting in a wheat sample with an OTA content of $4.9 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$. The
391 reference material was previously grounded to give particles sizes below 50 μm , as specified in section
392 2.3.1. The average concentration found ($4.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$) was included in the interval of concentration
393 certified by the manufacturer, indicating the accuracy of this method for the determination of OTA in wheat.

394

395 *3.6. Analysis of wheat samples*

396

397 Six wheat samples, including four varieties, were analysed in order to prove the suitability of the
398 proposed method for the routine control of OTA. None of them contained OTA at detectable levels. Table
399 4 shows the recoveries obtained after spiking the samples at three levels of concentration (3, 8 and 20 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$)
400 Kg^{-1}). Recoveries were expressed as the mean value of three independent determinations along with their

401 corresponding standard deviations. Recoveries were between 84 and 95% with relative standard
402 deviations ranging from 0.1 to 5%.

403 The chromatograms obtained from three different concentrations of OTA in water/ethanol/acetic
404 acid (49.5/49.5/1) and a sample of *Triticum aestivum*, fortified at three levels of concentration (3, 8 and 20
405 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$), are shown in the Figure 4A and B, respectively. No interference from matrix components was
406 detected for any of the samples analysed.

407

408 **4. Conclusions**

409

410 Supramolecular solvents consist of amphiphilic nanostructures that provide multiple binding sites
411 and regions of different polarity. These outstanding properties make them suitable to extract a variety of
412 analytes with high efficiency and render them ideal for microextractions. In this research, supramolecular
413 solvents made up of reverse micelles of decanoic acid in THF are proposed as valuable tools for the
414 microextraction of OTA from wheat, offering a simple, inexpensive and rapid alternative to conventional
415 sample preparation methods, which combine high solvent consumption with the need of clean-up and
416 solvent evaporation steps. The extraction procedure takes about 30 minutes; several samples can be
417 simultaneously extracted; requires a low sample amount (0.3 g wheat), which is made representative of
418 the bulk by reducing the particle size to $<50 \mu\text{m}$, and a low supramolecular solvent volume (350 μL);
419 conventional equipment in labs is used for extraction and features low cost. The method developed can
420 be used for the routine control of OTA in raw wheat below the tolerance level permitted by the European
421 Directives ($5 \mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$) [6]. Because most of raw and processed foods contain similar constituents than
422 wheat (e.g. carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, etc), the microextraction procedure here proposed could be
423 widely applicable to food residues with ability to establish hydrogen bonding and dispersion interactions
424 with the supramolecular solvent.

425

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431

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510 **Figure captions**

511

512 **Figure 1.** Scheme of the different steps followed for the analysis of OTA in cereals.

513

514 **Figure 2.** Phase diagram of ternary mixtures made up of tetrahydrofuran, decanoic acid and water in the
515 (a) absence and (b) presence of wheat (300 mg).

516

517 **Figure 3.** Recoveries for OTA at different wheat (mg)/decanoic acid (mg) ratios.

518

519 **Figure 4.** LC/Fluorescence chromatograms obtained from: (A) standard solutions of OTA in
520 water/ethanol/acetic acid (49.5/49.5/1); (a) 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, (b) 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and (c) 3 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; and (B) a 300 mg-
521 aliquot of *Triticum aestivum* spiked with OTA; (a) blank sample, (b) 3 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, (c) 8 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$ and (d) 20 μg
522 Kg^{-1} .

523

524

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Table 1.

Figures of merits of the linear relationship ($y = a + bx$) between the coacervate volume (y , μL) and the amount of decanoic acid (x , mg) at different THF percentages.

THF (%)	$b \pm S^a$ ($\mu\text{L mg}^{-1}$)	$a \pm S^a$ (μL)	R^{2b}
4	1.15 ± 0.03	-61 ± 6	0.998
6	1.30 ± 0.02	-66 ± 4	0.9992
8	1.39 ± 0.02	-65 ± 5	0.9990
9	1.42 ± 0.03	-46 ± 8	0.998
11	1.55 ± 0.06	-44 ± 13	0.995

^a standard deviation ; ^b correlation coefficient ; $n = 6$

Table 2.

Figures of merits of the exponential relationships ($y = b_0 e^{b_1 z}$) between the coacervate volume (y , μL) and the concentration of THF (z , %) at different amounts of decanoic acid.

Decanoic acid (mg)	$b_0 \pm S^a$ (μL)	$b_1 \pm S^a$	R^{2b}
125	55 \pm 4	0.092 \pm 0.009	0.97
150	86 \pm 5	0.069 \pm 0.007	0.97
200	127 \pm 5	0.062 \pm 0.004	0.990
250	179 \pm 6	0.059 \pm 0.004	0.990
300	224 \pm 9	0.057 \pm 0.005	0.98
350	277 \pm 6	0.056 \pm 0.003	0.995

^a standard deviation ; ^b correlation coefficient ; $n = 5$

Table 3. Mean percent recoveries (n=3) and standard deviations obtained for ochratoxin A in wheat (300 mg) as a function of the amount of decanoic acid and percentage of THF used for supramolecular solvent production

Decanoic acid (mg)	Recoveries \pm Standard deviations (%)				
	THF (%)				
	4%	6%	8%	9%	11%
125	49 \pm 2	61 \pm 1	63 \pm 3	57 \pm 4	57 \pm 3
150	59 \pm 2	67 \pm 2	70 \pm 4	60 \pm 2	63 \pm 2
200	66 \pm 4	72 \pm 2	75 \pm 6	69 \pm 5	70 \pm 2
250	73 \pm 3	77 \pm 6	80 \pm 2	74 \pm 5	75 \pm 4
300	77 \pm 6	86 \pm 3	94 \pm 2	87 \pm 2	79 \pm 6
350	79 \pm 1	80 \pm 2	81 \pm 2	76 \pm 6	Precipitate

Table 4. Mean recoveries and standard deviations obtained for OTA in the analysis of wheat samples using the proposed method

Concentration ($\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$)	Recovery \pm ^a Standard deviation (%)					
	Samples					
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
3	90 \pm 4	95 \pm 3	86 \pm 4	89 \pm 2	87 \pm 5	87.7 \pm 0.3
8	88 \pm 3	90 \pm 1	92 \pm 2	92 \pm 2	84 \pm 3	95 \pm 3
20	91 \pm 2	90 \pm 1	89.1 \pm 0.3	94 \pm 4	90 \pm 1	90.1 \pm 0.1

^a n=3

Wheat varieties: M1,M2: *Triticum durum*; M3: *Triticosecale*; M4,M6: *Triticum aestivum*; M5:

Hordeum-Triticum

Sample amount = 0.3 g